

On the Output Conductance Dispersion due to Traps and Self-Heating in Large Bulk, FDSOI and FinFET nMOS Devices

L. Tondelli¹, A. J. Scholten², R. Asanovski^{1,*}, R. M. T. Pijper², T. V. Dinh³, and L. Selmi¹

¹Dept. of Engineering “Enzo Ferrari”, Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia, Italy; *now with imec, Belgium

²NXP Semiconductors, Eindhoven, The Netherlands; ³NXP Semiconductors, Austin, USA;

corresponding author email: lisa.tondelli@unimore.it

Abstract—We report experimental investigations on the AC small signal output conductance (g_{DD}) of large nMOSFETs with bulk, FDSOI, and bulk FinFET architecture. The g_{DD} frequency spectra reveal opposite trends at low and high gate voltage V_{GS} . Furthermore, an unexpected anomaly is observed at V_{GS} close to the value where the sensitivity to temperature of the DC IV transfer characteristics changes sign.

Self-heating is scrutinized as a possible unique origin of the g_{DD} dispersion. An additional non-negligible role of trap states is put in evidence by numerical simulations taking self-consistently into account electrothermal effects and the possible presence of gate dielectric traps.

The results can reduce inaccuracies in determining the thermal resistances from the g_{DD} frequency dispersion data, and support better design of large FETs and circuits for RF applications.

Index Terms—Bulk MOSFET, Bulk FinFET, FDSOI MOSFET, Self-Heating, Traps

I. INTRODUCTION

Output conductance dispersion has been studied in the past, especially in III-V semiconductor devices [1]–[3] and bipolar transistors [4]. Several works on GaAs MESFETs and HEMTs focus on the frequency dispersion of the AC parameters [5], [6], and attribute the deviations from the DC values to traps in the buffer layer below the channel or at the interface with the access regions [7]. It is fundamental to account for these effects in designing microwave circuits and in defining accurate large-signal device models for analog, mixed-signal, and high-power circuits [1].

Silicon devices usually feature much smaller trap densities than III-V FETs. Furthermore, in bulk transistors, the traps are not located in a semi-insulating substrate below the channel but in the gate stack dielectrics or at the dielectric-channel interface. Large MOSFETs fabricated in advanced CMOS technology nodes, as needed in RF Systems on Chip (SoCs) also suffer from remarkable self-heating effects, with notable consequences on both static and AC small signal characteristics [8], [9]. Indeed, works on large transistors attribute the g_{DD} rise at high frequency to the reduced impact that Self-Heating Effects (SHEs) have on the drain current at those

frequencies [8], [10], and even use this frequency dispersion to quantitatively characterize the thermal resistance and SHEs [11]. Moreover, the use of high- κ gate dielectrics and ultra thin Si layers can lead to non-negligible concentrations of interface and bulk insulator defects [12], which are also known to cause frequency dispersion of the AC small signal parameters (e.g., g_m and g_{DD}).

In this work, firstly we report experiments on multi-channel bulk MOSFETs, multi-channel Fully Depleted Silicon On Insulator (FDSOI) MOSFETs, and large multi-fin multi-finger bulk FinFETs, all exhibiting a V_{GS} -dependent g_{DD} frequency dispersion. As V_{GS} approaches the value where $dI_D/dT \approx 0$ (hereafter denoted $V_{GS,INV}$), the g_{DD} curves exhibit a non-monotonic trend (decreasing at low frequency and increasing at high frequency). In contrast, the trend is only increasing or decreasing at low and high gate voltage, respectively.

To unveil the origin of this opposite behaviour at low and high V_{GS} , and of the anomaly at $V_{GS} \approx V_{GS,INV}$, (so far unreported to the best of our knowledge), we consider both the delays of the heat dissipation pathways and the coexistence of SHEs and charge-trapping effects. Extensive simulations, calibrated on experiments, highlight the effects in each bias and frequency range.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II reports the measured results. Sections III and IV illustrate the simulation results and propose two possible explanations and Section V draws the conclusions.

II. EXPERIMENTS

Experiments were carried out on devices fabricated with three commercial CMOS technologies having Hafnia-based high- κ metal gate stacks: interdigitated bulk and FDSOI MOSFETs, and multi-channel bulk FinFETs. The effective channel width, W_{eff} , length, L_{eff} , and number of channels, N_{ch} , are given in Tab. I together with other key device parameters.

Fig. 1 depicts the normalized, experimental output conductance curves versus frequency in saturation

$$g_{DD,n}(f) = \frac{g_{DD}(f) - g_{DD,HF}}{g_{DD,HF}} \quad (1)$$

TABLE I: Main parameters of the devices of interest for this work. Note the smaller V_{DS} of the FDSOI device.

Metric	Bulk	FinFET	FDSOI
V_T (V)	0.33	0.23	0.27
$V_{DS} = V_{GS}$ (V)	1.0	1.0	0.8
$V_{GS,INV}$ (V)	0.67	0.53	0.6
f_{HF} (GHz)	6.37	4.51	5.06
N_{ch} (-)	4	24	4
W_{eff} (μm)	1.5	2.2	0.4
L_{eff} (nm)	≈ 30	≈ 20	≈ 20
R_{th} (K/W)	$5.72 \cdot 10^3$	$8.16 \cdot 10^4$	$6.19 \cdot 10^4$
ΔT (K)	35.2	170	63.8

Fig. 1: $g_{DD,n}$ frequency dispersion observed in experiments for bulk MOSFETs (top), 6-fins, 4-fingers multichannel bulk FinFETs (middle) and FDSOI MOSFETs (bottom).

Here, $g_{DD,HF} = g_{DD}(f_{HF})$ is the output conductance at a frequency, f_{HF} , high enough to be unaffected by SHEs but not as high as to be affected by parasitics. We found that, f_{HF} is largely independent of V_{GS} , although sometimes difficult to be precisely defined if the data is noisy.

We see in Fig. 1 that all transistors show a similar g_{DD} behavior as a function of frequency and gate voltage in the explored V_{GS} range, which includes the $V_{GS,INV}$ values where an almost zero temperature coefficient is observed. Fig. 2 shows typical $I_D - V_{GS}$ curves at different chuck temperatures for the bulk FinFET, and highlights the position of the $V_{GS,INV}$ (values in Tab. I). The device overtemperature in saturation (estimated according to [11]) is the largest for FinFETs and the smallest for bulk MOSFETs. The FDSOI MOSFET data lies in-between, but the exact value reflects a smaller V_{DS} .

When $V_{GS} > V_{GS,INV}$, the curves in Fig. 1 start from a negative value and then converge to about zero at f_{HF} , as

Fig. 2: Typical $I_D - V_{GS}$ curves of the FinFET transistors at different chuck temperatures. $V_{GS,INV}$ is the V_{GS} value where the drain current dependence on temperature changes its sign.

Fig. 3: Normalized output conductance curves for the bulk, FinFET and FDSOI devices at $V_{GS} \approx V_{GS,INV}$.

expected based on self-heating effects. When $V_{GS} < V_{GS,INV}$, instead, the curves start from a positive value and then decrease down to zero. For the case when $V_{GS} \approx V_{GS,INV}$ (see zoom in Fig. 3), we observe the anomalous g_{DD} behavior, i.e., the $g_{DD,n}$ first decreases and then increases.

III. SIMULATIONS: SELF-HEATING ONLY

In a first attempt to explain the experiments, we focus on the dynamics of SHEs. At high V_{GS} , static power dissipation deteriorates the mobility, decreases the I_D and generates a negative $g_{DD,n}$. Conversely, at low V_{GS} , the device heating affects the surface potential at threshold and possibly the metal work function as well, thus lowering the V_T [13], [14], and resulting in a positive $g_{DD,n}$. The gate metal is separated from the hot spot where the maximum power density is dissipated by multiple interfaces and ultra-thin layers with remarkably degraded transverse thermal conductivity $k_{th,\perp}$ and small thermal capacitance [15]–[17]. Therefore, we expect the variations of the gate temperature to be smaller and delayed with respect to those of the channel. At low frequency, the temperature modulation has enough time to fully propagate to the gate, so the V_T modulation could prevail, thus explaining the positive $g_{DD,n}$. At higher frequencies, the temperature modulation may not propagate to the gate [8], and the local modulation of the mobility could prevail. Indeed, when $V_{GS} \approx V_{GS,INV}$, both positive and negative g_{DD} shifts are visible at distinct frequencies, which could be a signature of the different thermal time constants of the channel and the gate (Fig. 3).

To validate this hypothesis, we used 3D numerical simulations of the 6-fins 4-fingers FinFET (the architecture exhibiting

Fig. 4: Simulated temperature transients at four locations in the hottest FinFET channel (bottom sketch) normalized to the respective maximum excursion during the rise from 0 V to 1 V, (left) and fall from 1 V to 0 V (right) of V_{GS} . $V_{DS}=1$ V.

the larger SHEs), calibrated on experimental DC IV curves and AC characteristics at $V_{GS}=V_{DS}=1$ V. We run transient simulations in response to a 0.5 ps V_{GS} step from 0 V to 1 V (rise) and from 1 V to 0 V (fall) at constant $V_{DS} = 1$ V. Fig. 4 depicts the normalized overtemperature of the hottest channel versus time:

$$\Delta T_n(t) = \frac{T(t) - T(0)}{T_f - T(0)}, \quad (2)$$

at the locations shown in the sketch of Fig. 4. Here, $T(0)$ and T_f are the temperature before the gate voltage step and the final, steady state temperature, respectively. Despite there being a delay in the heating and cooling of the gate compared to the channel, this is only about a factor of $2\times$ at 50% of the temperature excursion, which is insufficient to explain the large frequency difference (in Fig. 3) in the frequency where the $g_{DD,n}$ drifts from its low-frequency value and the frequency where it starts increasing toward the high-frequency one. Similar results are obtained at lower V_{GS} .

To corroborate this observation, we made an attempt to further delay the gate heating, by artificially reducing of an additional factor 5 the k_{th} of the ultra-thin SiO_2 and HfO_2 layers separating the channel from the gate with respect to reported values [16], [17]. This pessimistic underestimate of k_{th} degradation yields a modest increase in the gate heating delay (not shown), thus leaving the previous considerations unaltered. Moreover, at $V_{GS} \approx V_{GS,INV}$ the hot spot in the channel shows modest SHEs. Even assuming a much larger temperature coefficient of the gate metal work function than reported e.g. in [18], we could not observe a g_{DD} dispersion as pronounced as in experiments. These results suggest that the g_{DD} anomaly cannot be ascribed solely to SHEs.

Fig. 5: Measured and simulated DC IV curves of the bulk MOSFET. Right: $V_{DS}=50$ mV. Left: I_D - V_{GS} curve at at $V_{DS}=1$ V and I_D - V_{DS} at $V_{GS}=1$ V.

IV. SIMULATIONS: SELF-HEATING AND TRAPS

It is widely recognized that traps in the substrate and the dielectrics can cause significant frequency dispersion of the transconductance and output conductance of FET devices in both Silicon and III-V materials, especially at low V_{GS} [1], [19]. To investigate if traps could be the missing physical ingredient explaining the observed g_{DD} dispersion, we consider bulk and FDSOI MOSFETs because of the much smaller $g_{DD,n}$ at $V_{GS} > V_{GS,INV}$ than for large 6-fins 4-fingers FinFETs. We initially incorporated a uniform distribution of traps in both energy and space into the TCAD model, with a density $N_{TR} = 3 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ eV}^{-1}$ (in line with [20]) within the SiO_2 interlayer between the channel and the high- κ insulator. Traps in the bulk of the high- κ material are neglected, due to their modest electrostatic coupling to the channel; hence, negligible contribution to the drain current noise.

We calibrated the electrothermal numerical model, incorporating gate dielectric traps using bulk MOSFET data, and achieved the excellent agreement shown in Fig. 5. Then, we applied the same simulation setup to the FDSOI transistor (which features a shorter channel length but maintains the same SiO_2 thickness). We utilized the same trap distribution and we obtained FDSOI DC curves (not shown) that closely match the experiments. While not fully quantitative (no explicit effort was made to fit the trap distributions to experiments), these simulations are based on realistic trap density values and provide indications about the adequacy of the trap mechanism in explaining the g_{DD} dispersion anomaly.

Fig. 6 left reports the simulated $g_{DD,n}$ for bulk and FDSOI MOSFETs. The trapping time, τ_{TR} , has been adjusted via the Huang-Rhys factor to emphasize the separation of the trap effects and SHEs in the frequency domain. The extended frequency range of the plot, compared to that in Fig. 1, highlights that above $f_{TR} \approx 1/\tau_{TR} \approx 100$ Hz the trap distribution responds only in part to the AC signal. At $f > f_{TR}$, the g_{DD} decreases because traps do not respond quickly enough to the AC voltage since the detrapping time is comparable to, or greater than, the signal period [1], [2]. The g_{DD} curves also exhibit slope changes at f_{SH} , representing the point where

Fig. 6: Simulated g_{DD} frequency dispersion in bulk MOSFET (left) and FDSOI MOSFET (right) with SHEs and traps, showing qualitatively similar behavior as the experiments.

Fig. 7: Simulated g_{DD} frequency dispersion for the bulk MOSFET at $V_{DS}=1$ V without traps (SHE only, left) or without SH (traps only, right).

SHEs become less significant because the AC signal period becomes smaller than the thermal time constant. Both f_{TR} and f_{SH} are almost independent of V_{GS} .

The relative importance of traps and SH in shaping the dispersion of the output conductance can be fully appreciated by comparing electrothermal simulations where we remove the traps from the dielectric (Fig. 7 left) to simulations where we use a simple isothermal drift-diffusion transport model, thereby eliminating SHEs (Fig. 7 right). Here we observe that SHEs alone can generate a positive $g_{DD,n}$ at low V_{GS} (due to retarded heating of the gate with respect to the channel and surface potential drift with temperature) but the effect is too small to fully explain the experiment.

It is also interesting to note that if we change the trap type from acceptor to donor maintaining the same trap concentration (see Fig. 8, left), no visible difference is found in the $g_{DD,n}$, regardless of the V_{GS} . Indeed, although the trapped charge within the SiO_2 layer is negative for acceptors and positive for donors, in both cases, electrons are detrapped as the drain voltage increases and the quasi-Fermi level on the drain side approaches the trap level. The electron detrapping process increases the channel charge and the I_D , regardless of traps being acceptors or donors. Fig. 8, right confirms this interpretation by showing that at low V_{DS} , the charge

Fig. 8: Left: $g_{DD,n}$ frequency dispersion for donor and acceptor traps. Right: absolute value of the trapped charge in the SiO_2 interlayer versus V_{DS} .

in acceptors is high and then gradually decreases (release of electrons from traps). Conversely, the positive charge in donors increases, signifying the release of electrons and the acquisition of a positive charge. Both phenomena increase the drain current; hence, the trap effect on the g_{DD} is independent on the trap type, and the g_{DD} dispersion cannot be used to assess the trap type.

V. CONCLUSION

We investigated by experiments and simulations an anomalous output conductance frequency dispersion whereby devices with different architectures but somehow similar gate stacks exhibit a non-monotonic frequency dependence of the $g_{DD,n}$ at $V_{GS} \approx V_{GS,INV}$. Self-heating can provide the essential ingredients to explain a sign change in the $g_{DD,n}$, due to delays in the heat propagation between the hot spot and the gate, but only the combined effect of dielectric traps and SHEs provides a credible explanation of the experiments.

The detailed insights provided by this study contribute to better understand if and when traps affect the analog performance of modern MOS transistors, support device optimization, and the development of devices and circuits with improved analog performance and reduced anomalies.

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